

FORWARD D3.1 Thematic working groups and thematic action plans methodology

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Document description:	<p>D3.1 Thematic working groups and thematic action plans methodology (Forward Description of Work).</p> <p>For each thematic working group, the list of members, the management, the sub-coordinator will be specified, as well as the scope of the thematic that will be tackled.</p> <p>A common methodology as a reference for the work of thematic working groups for the definition of the thematic action plans will be produced after the first transnational meeting of the sub-coordinators of the thematic working groups.</p>

Authors List

Organization	Name
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Table of content

1 Introduction	3
2 TWGs definition	4
1.1 Identification of R&I thematics	4
1.1.1 Building the inter-regional TWGs	5
1.1.2 Selection Criteria	5
1.2 The role of the Steering Committee	6
1.3 Risks for implementation	6
1.4 WP3 coordination team	6
2 TWGs: roles and management	7
2.1 TWGs roles	7
2.2 Organisation and planning of the activities.....	8
2.2.1 Proposed calendar	9
2.3 Communication activities	10
2.4 Joining a TWG.....	10
3 TWGs: thematic scope, sub coordinators, management team and members.....	11
3.1 TWG management teams.....	11
3.2 TWG registrations.....	12
TWG 1 Health and applied medical technologies, diagnostics and therapies.....	12
TWG 2 Social science and social innovation	13
TWG 3 Earth system, space & universe science	15
TWG 4 Information & communications technology	16
TWG 5 Climate change & Energy transition	17
TWG 6 Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and biosystems engineering....	18
TWG 7 Biodiversity conservation & restoration.....	19
TWG 8 Marine sciences & technologies	20
4 Thematic Action Plan methodology	21
4.1 Designing and implementing the strategy	21
4.2 Action Plan Development	22
4.3 Results and deliverables.....	22
5 Annexes.....	23
<i>Annex I TWGs List of members / registrations.....</i>	<i>23</i>
<i>Annex II TWGs Action plan template.....</i>	<i>24</i>

1 Introduction

According to FORWARD objectives, critical mass and connectivity among ORs and between ORs and continental Europe are some of the main obstacles ORs faced with to access EU framework programme. The aim of work package 3 (Co-creation and implementation of thematic working plans) is to reinforce the actual and reveal the potential competitive advantages of Outermost Regions in their respective research and innovation fields of expertise, and the identification of common interests.

To overcome this need, the present deliverable helps the OR partners to build and manage a number of thematic working groups (TWGs), composed by experts from ORs, other European regions / countries and Third countries, as well as to define and implement thematic action plans for each group with the feedback of ORs' R&I communities.

This document is based on the experience of the Enterprise Europe Network¹ sector groups, and adapted to FORWARD needs.

¹ <http://een.ec.europa.eu/>

2 TWGs definition

The TWGs will bring together experts from ORs, European regions / countries and Third countries' institutions that operate in a common strategic domain, identified in the WP2 diagnosis of ORs research and innovation ecosystems. Then, TWGs are inter-regional and based on common interest of ORs.

The TWGs **general objectives** are:

- Prospective and strategic exercises to identify critical research fields and subjects in the ORs.
- Establishment of **networks** between the OR and external actors that will cooperate to build **critical masses and projects** on the considered thematics.
- Implement the activities envisaged in a specific domain.
- Prospective approach to focus on ensuring their **sustainability** both during the project life and even after its end.

1.1 Identification of R&I thematics

Following WP2 results, the diagnosis of ORs research and innovation ecosystems allowed identifying the common thematic among ORs, based on:

- RIS3 domains (already described in FORWARD proposal).
- Ranking on total EU Contribution (including domains with only 1 OR involved).
- Ranking of the different fields of expertise (at least 2 ORs, FP + other EU funds).
- Potential fields of cooperation between the ORs.

Additionally, it was taken into account the:

- Alignment with the Horizon Europe pillars² and clusters.
- Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations³.

The table 1 identifies the eight TWGs selected and approved by FORWARD Steering Committee. Initially, it was also identify a TWG on tourism and ecotourism that finally merged with social science and social innovation.

Table 1: FORWARD thematic working groups.

TWG1	Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies.
TWG2	Social sciences and social innovation.
TWG3	Earth system, space & universe sciences.
TWG4	Information and Communications Technology.
TWG5	Climate change and Energy transition.
TWG6	Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering.
TWG7	Biodiversity conservation and restoration.
TWG8	Marine sciences & technologies.

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme_en

³ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/>

1.1.1 Building the inter-regional TWGs

The Steering Committee validated the TWGs, prioritizing those of higher interest among the partners, and each OR worked in the identification of **members**, in the thematic areas where it could get involved. The members are individuals from R&I organizations or from other stakeholders who have a direct involvement in the selected areas. In order to coordinate the identification of these members, ORs designated a [Regional Coordinator of R&I community](#) at the beginning of the project, who is in charge of the communication with the R&D institutions at their region.

Figure 1: Governance for building TWGs.

The WP3 leader (ITC) was responsible for collecting the information through a [Registration Form](#), where the member could include: first name, last name, region, organisation, position, field of expertise, email, thematic working group, link to CV and their interest to become **sub coordinator** of the group.

The TWGs were built in two phases:

- PHASE 1, at regional level, the FORWARD R&I partners (ULL, ULPGC, PLOCAN, ITC, IAC, UAc, CCIA, UMa, UR, UA, UG, GDI, Synergile, CCISM, CE) proposed R&I members for each TWG and the [Regional Coordinator of R&I community](#) (GOBCAN, FRCT, ARDITI, NEXA, CTM, CTG, REG GUA, COMSM and CDM) validated the regional sub-coordinator among the candidates.
- PHASE 2, at inter-regional level, the WP3 leader (ITC) compiled all the information and the full list of sub-coordinator candidates. A short list of candidates was proposed to the SC for final selection.

1.1.2 Selection Criteria

The selection criteria defined the requirements to launch a TWG and select a sub coordinator.

Thematic Working Groups:

- The TWG should involve at least 3 ORs with a minimum of 5 members from 3 different organizations.
- The TWG should have at least one candidate for sub-coordination, validated by the OR.

Sub-coordinator:

- R&I profile with expertise in the area.
- Validated by the [Regional Coordinator of R&I community](#).
- Expertise in European R&D projects, coordination or WP leadership.

- Highly motivated.
- CV + scientific indicators in the last 5 years:
 1. Most relevant articles related to the TWG published.
 2. Research projects managed as PI related to the TWG subsidised by official bodies.
 3. Participation in research projects related to the TWG subsidised by official bodies.
 4. Doctoral theses directed (concluded).
 5. Patents obtained.
 6. National/International mobility experience.

1.2 The role of the Steering Committee

Even if TWG are primarily based on a bottom-up approach, the SC will closely follow the activities in order to ensure that the substantial resources invested into the TWG are efficient.

1.3 Risks for implementation

Within the framework of FORWARD WP3, some critical risks that might affect project implementation have been identified:

Table 2: Risk for implementation.

Risk description WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Lack of participation or commitment of sub coordinators of the thematic working groups	<p>Preventive measure: Sub coordinators of Thematic Working Groups were selected on the basis of already demonstrated interest and commitment towards the thematic they will have to work on. Additionally a facilitator from the same OR was identified.</p> <p>Corrective measure: Where a specific sub coordinator will repeatedly miss to project activities, it will be substituted with another one. In case no substitute is available a representative selected from one of the 9 partner organisations represented in the FORWARD Steering Committee will be chosen considering her/his experience and relevance for the thematic working group.</p>

1.4 WP3 coordination team

In the table below there are the organizations and the reference person for each task of the WP3.

Table 2: WP3 coordination team.

List of Tasks	Leader	Person	email
WP3 Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans	ITC	Alma Cruz	forward@itccanarias.org
3.1 Building thematic working group in key common strategic fields of expertise	ITC	Lucía Dobarro Antonella Pugliese Iñigo Oramas	
3.2 Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans	SYNERGILE	Jean-François Dorville	emyly.guyon@synergile.fr amelie.belfort@synergile.fr jean-francois.dorville@synergile.fr
3.3 Sustainability of thematic working groups		Emyly Guyon Amélie Belfort	

2 TWGs: roles and management

2.1 TWGs roles

Each TWG is managed by a team composed by a sub coordinator, a deputy (optional) and a facilitator. The TWG is composed by members, who express their interest to join the group through a registration form.

- The **sub coordinator**, selected by the Steering Committee, is the chairperson of the TWG.
- The **deputy**, appointed by the sub coordinator, supports the sub coordinator and / or replaces him / her, when necessary.
- The **facilitator**, appointed by the same OR than the sub coordinator, supports both, the sub-coordinator and deputy in the management and tasks.

The TWG sub-coordinator and the deputy (if applicable), with the support of the facilitator, are **responsible** for:

- Managing the TWG, web-meetings and online communication tools.
- Writing the TWG Action Plan.
- Coordination with other members of the group, in order to share and integrate the contributions from all regions.
- Coordinating WP5 Networking activities in the TWG.
- Communicating within other TWG and the WP3 Forward coordination team.
- Reporting data for each event / activity, writing a yearly narrative report.

TWGs are required to set up a structured mechanism to share the work. The Sub-coordinator – supported by the deputy - will always remain in charge of the overall coordination and will represent the TWG to external actors. Beyond that, a number of tasks could be delegated to the facilitator and other TWG members:

- Updating the Action Plan.
- Updating the intranet and the public TWG internet page (see communication activities).
- Ensuring that the list of members is updated.
- Promoting specific projects for the group.
- Liaising with other TWGs.
- Connecting with external stakeholders.

Participating in a TWG as a sub-coordinator, deputy or facilitator requires a substantial commitment of working time. The resources invested need to be translated into concrete results that have a positive impact on the sector. It is therefore very important for TWG management team to be aware of the high level of commitment. Additionally, sub coordinators will be covered for travel costs and venues for events related with Forward project activities.

Figure 2: TWG governance

TWG sub coordinators are expected to attend at least three **transregional meetings** with the sub coordinators of all the TWGs. Due to Covid-19 travel restrictions, the meetings will take place online and, when possible, they will take place onsite, in combination with other Forward activities:

- The **kick-off meeting** online: it is the first transregional meeting that will take place at the beginning of the exercise, to ensure that the TWG will implement the same methodology and share questions. This meeting will be followed by an **initial training** to launch the TWG and manage their action plan design in an efficient and collaborative manner.
- A **second transregional meeting** between sub-coordinators will allow them to exchange on the work progress, share good practices and difficulties.
- The **last meeting**, if possible, may take place in Brussels in a piggy backing spirit, to present the action plans and prospective approach.

Last, but not least, each sub-coordinator will share the work at mid-term with the **Advisory Board** of the project to collect their inputs and feedback online.

2.2 Organisation and planning of the activities

The sub-coordinators will be officially informed about its selection by the WP3 leader (ITC) and invited to a **kick-off meeting**, where they will meet each other and their main duties, tasks, milestones and deadlines will be presented by the WP3 Forward coordination team (ITC and Synergile).

Once, the deputy and facilitator are assigned to each thematic group, these management teams will attend a common **initial training**, where the Thematic Working Group Methodology will be presented in detail, providing digital tools for managing the groups and prepare / manage the action plans design in an efficient and appropriate collaborative manner. It will also provide some methodology to develop prospective approach and manage the online communities. This training will include the following topics:

- Thematic Working Groups in Forward: Mission and objectives.
- TWG Management Team: Roles and responsibilities.
- The Collaborative Space: the management team will receive capacitation about setting up the collaborative space (Microsoft Teams) and managing it.
- Designing and implementing the strategy.
- Action Plan Development.
- Results/ Deliverables.

2.2.1 Proposed calendar

Communication to the sub-coordinators (ITC). Email presentation to the selected sub coordinators. Invitation to the kick-off meeting and training.	August 2020
1st Transregional meeting: Kick-off meeting with TWG sub-coordinators: (All sub-coordinators, WP3 leaders and SC). Presentation of the FORWARD project and the thematic shortlisted + Introduction of the sub coordinators, deputy selection. Online.	September 2020
1st Transregional meeting: Initial training: (All sub-coordinators, deputies and facilitators, WP3 leaders). Training on a common methodology. WP3 next steps. Online.	October 2020
Follow up session with all TWG.	December 2020
Individual TWG meetings: (each TGW, sub-coordinator, deputy and members) presentation of the FORWARD project. Introduction of the members (online)	December 2020 – January 2021
TWG meetings (each TGW, sub-coordinator, deputy and members): Work on the definition of action plans.	January – February 2021
2nd Transregional meeting, All sub-coordinators (if not available can be replaced by the deputy): work progress, good practices and difficulties.	February 2021
TWG action plans delivery, first version.	March 2021
Regional workshops: Each Regional Coordinator of R&I + experts + other regional stakeholders	

<p>Meeting with the Advisory Board (Each sub-coordinator - if not available can be replaced by the deputy): Sub-coordinator will share the work with the Advisory Board of the project to collect their inputs and feedback.</p>	<p>June or September 2021</p>
<p>At least 2 TWG meetings: (each TGW, sub-coordinator, deputy and members): Work on action plan implementation. Potential invitation to other International Experts + Regional Contact Points + other regional stakeholders (online)</p>	<p>April 2021 – June 2022</p>
<p>3rd Transregional meeting. Final meeting: (Each sub-coordinator - if not available can be replaced by the deputy) : Presentation of the action plan and the prospective approach in Brussels</p>	<p>End of Forward project, June 2022</p>

2.3 Communication activities

TWGs are encouraged to cooperate with other TWGs and with relevant stakeholders outside FORWARD network, such as representatives from European and Third countries institutions, and European experts, Commission services, etc.

[FORWARD webpage](#) is made available to each TWG to inform the public about its activities and results. This page should be the main public channel for the publication of TWG events and activities and should be seen as a way to increase the visibility of each TWG, in coordination with WP5 networking activities and WP8 dissemination and communication.

Each TWG will have a virtual space through Microsoft Teams. It is strongly recommended to use this rather than personal e-mail addresses for all official communication within the TWG in order to make sure that no information is lost due to out-of-date mailing lists, etc. Members of each TWG are advised to subscribe to the automatic alerts in order to be notified when there is a new post in their TWG forum.

2.4 Joining a TWG

All new applications for membership must be made via the **sub coordinator** and communicated to the [Regional Coordinator of R&I community](#) and [WP3 coordination team](#).

3 TWGs: thematic scope, sub coordinators, management team and members

3.1 TWG management teams

TWG	Management team	OR
1. Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies	Sub-coordinator, Jacob Lorenzo-Morales (University of La Laguna) Facilitators, Paloma Bernal and Elizabeth Carrillo (ULL)	Canary Islands
2. Social sciences and social innovation	Sub-coordinator, Philippe Jean-Pierre (Université de La Réunion) Facilitators, Philippe Holstein and Evelyne Tarnus (NEXA)	Réunion
3. Earth, space & universe sciences	Sub-coordinator, Pedro Silva (AIR Centre) Deputy: Mariana Avila, (AIR Centre) Facilitators, Marta Vergilio and Lina Silveira (FRCT) and Eduardo Braga (CCIA)	Azores
4. Information and Communications Technology ⁴	Sub-coordinator, Martine Collard (University of Antilles) Deputy, Wilfried Segretier (University of Antilles) Facilitators, Anthony Nobour (CTM) and Jean-François Dorville (Synergile)	Guadeloupe and Martinique
5. Climate change and Energy transition	Sub-coordinator, Claudio Mantero (Horários do Funchal) Deputy, Filipe Oliveira (AREAM) Facilitator, Lúcio Quintal (ARDITI)	Madeira
6. Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and biosystems engineering	Sub-coordinator, Jean-Christophe BAMBOU (INRAE) Facilitators, Emyly Guyon and Jean-François Dorville (Synergîle)	Guadeloupe
7. Biodiversity conservation and restoration	Sub-coordinator, Paulo Borges (University of Azores) Deputy, Mário Boieiro (University of Azores) Facilitators, Carolina Parelho and Lina Silveira (FRCT) and Nuno Vasconcelos (UAc)	Azores
8. Marine sciences & technologies	Sub-coordinator, Ricardo Haroun (University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria) Deputy, Francisco Otero Ferrer (ULPGC) Facilitators, Almudena Suárez and Noelia Díaz (ULPGC)	Canary Islands

⁴ TWG4 Sub-coordinator Ms. Collard (officially replaced by Mr. Segretier starting from April 2021)

3.2 TWG registrations

TWG 1 Health and applied medical technologies, diagnostics and therapies

Definition: The development and fostering of a stronger health system is important for ORs regions due to their distance from Continental Europe and isolation. Likewise, ORs can contribute to the development of R&I related with tropical disease and so on, and being an strategic referent for Third Countries neighbours because of their geographic location and their geostrategic positioning. Some scientific domains of expertise and policy objectives are:

- Study of tropical diseases.
- Development of tools for diagnosis.
- Monitoring and treatment of diseases.
- Pharmacology.
- Public health and Clinical medicine.
- Regenerative medicine.
- Epidemiology and health risk management.
- Health and demographic change.
- Obesity, diabetes and metabolic diseases prevention.
- Nutrition and health education.
- One health approach.
- Study of tropical infectious diseases.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3.

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Jacob Lorenzo-Morales, University of La Laguna (Canary Islands) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: -
- Facilitators: Paloma Bernal and Elizabeth Carrillo, ULL (Canary Islands)

Members and field of expertise: 66 registrations.

TWG 2 Social science and social innovation

Definition: Given their diversity and common social problems, the ORs are increasingly engaged in a process of social change to reduce fragility and develop new “enablers” for sustainable economic development. On the other hand, tourism is an important economic sector in the ORs, in terms of economic development and job creation, and is included in the RIS3 priorities of the smart specialization strategy in many ORs regions (Canary Islands, Madeira, Açores, Réunion...). Due to its impact, it is important to improve our services and knowledge in relation with the ecosystem and the environmental sustainability, in a way to preserve our territories from massive tourism and its impact. Some of the underlying areas of research and services are:

- Methods and tools for social regulation or methods for analysing and understanding social relations.
- Initial and continuing training.
- Education and training policies.
- The fostering of entrepreneurship.
- Ecosystem of interconnected applications (ICT)
- Database management.
- Sharing Economy.
- Social integration.
- Psychology and Occupational psychology.
- Sociology.
- Negotiation skills.
- Ergonomics.
- Global History.
- Cultural heritage.
- Colonial & postcolonial societies & economies.
- Island/small economies.
- Vulnerability and sustainability of small island economies.
- Island metabolism.
- Regional innovation systems & policies.
- Multicultural societies.
- Learning in multilingual context.
- Migration.
- Silver economy.
- Social inequalities and inclusion.
- Gender studies and equality.
- Environmental law.
- Environmental justice.
- Ecotones.
- Improving the competitiveness and productivity of the ORs tourism product.
- Productive diversification based on tourism.
- Sustainable leadership in tourism.
- Reduce the production and improve the valorisation of waste induced by tourism activities.
- Cultural services.
- Social integration.
- Employment, training and human resources in tourism.
- Innovation in design for the tourism sector.
- Strategic planning of tourists destinations.
- Touristic demand predictions.
- Smart planning of touristic routes at destination.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Culture, creativity and inclusive society) & (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3.

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Philippe Jean-Pierre, Université de La Réunion (Réunion) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: -
- Facilitators: Philippe Holstein and Evelyne Tarnus, NEXA (Réunion)

Members and field of expertise: 65 registrations.

development (6) economy (3) environment (3) information (3)
management (5) marketing (3) sustainable (5) technology (3)
tourism (18)

citizen (3) cultural (3) development (4) **economics** (11)
education (9)
entrepreneurship (10) environment (3)
environmental (5) gender (3) **health** (6) inequality (4)
innovation (12) **law** (10) legal (3) management (4)
psychology (3) public (5) research (4) **sciences** (7)
social (23) **studies** (6)

TWG 3 Earth system, space & universe science

Definition: ORs are facing different kinds of geological threats, like volcanic activity, forest fires, or relevant seismic activity. ORs have also some of the most privileged sites for astronomical observation. The ORs contribute to the development of Earth system, Space & Universe Sciences in the EU due to its geostrategic positioning, as several projects are implemented in the ORs on this field. Some fields of research/expertise are:

- Astrophysical research and astrophysical instrumentation.
- Astrobiology, Astroinformatics and Geoinformatics.
- Aerospace engineering and monitoring.
- Earth observations satellites and remote sensing.
- Natural risks related to climate change, meteorology, land cover change, soil erosion, etc.
- Physics of earth's interior, seismology, volcanology.
- Very large data bases: archiving, handling and analysis.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Industry, digital and space) & (Cluster: civil security for society)

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Pedro Silva, AIR Centre (Azores) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: Mariana Avila, AIR Centre (Azores)
- Facilitator: Marta Vergilio and Lina Silveira, FRCT and Eduardo Braga, CCIA (Azores)

Members and field of expertise: 30 registrations.

TWG 4 Information & communications technology

Definition: Due to their multidisciplinary nature, ICT plays a transversal role in all thematic areas, such as application or integration, which gives them flexibility and agility in positioning innovation in the market, with great impact. This area should be looked at for its involvement in a significant variety and consequent impact on the regional and global economy. A key area at local, regional, national and global levels is e-government. Some scientific domains of expertise and policy objectives are:

- Economic development.
- Public administration.
- Network infrastructure: full broadband coverage of high speed.
- Inclusion (a collective awareness platform about poverty support measures).
- Digital growth: widespread use of advanced IS services by companies and citizens.
- Digital Single Market.
- Education.
- Health (telemedicine for remote islands).
- Biodiversity.
- Ocean and maritime.
- Climate change management.
- Tourism.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Industry, digital and space) & (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3.

Management team⁵:

- Sub-coordinator: Martine Collard, University of Antilles (Guadeloupe) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: Wilfried Segretier, University of Antilles (Martinique) / [CV](#)
- Facilitators: Anthony Nobour, CTM (Martinique) and Jean-François Dorville, Synergile (Guadeloupe)

Members and field of expertise: 49 registrations.

⁵ TWG4 Sub-coordinator Ms. Collard (officially replaced by Mr. Segretier starting from April 2021)

TWG 5 Climate change & Energy transition

Definition: ORs are especially vulnerable to global warming, in particular, to the rise in sea level and extreme weather conditions. Likewise, the ORs disperse and isolated geographical location in the globe provides a unique opportunity to study its interactions with land and atmosphere. Observations that are organized on a systematic basis for process understanding and model development, or other research or demonstration purposes. ORs have excellent renewable energy resources but they are not being used to their full extent for technical, economic and legislative barriers. Legislative barriers are mostly at national level. Moreover, the situation among ORs is heterogeneous. Some scientific domains of expertise and policy objectives are:

- Climatology and climate change.
- Terrestrial ecology, land cover change.
- Forecasting and integration of variable renewables in isolated electricity grids.
- Energy efficiency, both thermal and electric, including bioclimatic architecture.
- Integration of variable renewables in (isolated) electricity grids.
- Small -and medium scale stand- alone energy systems.
- Smart grids, including micro- and mini-grids and hybrid systems.
- Transport electrification / decarbonisation.
- “New” renewable energies such as high enthalpy geothermal energy, off-shore wind energy, wave energy, ocean thermal energy conversion...
- Energy storage.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Climate, energy and mobility) & (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3.

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Claudio Mantero, Horários do Funchal (Madeira) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: Filipe Oliveira, AREAM (Madeira)
- Facilitator: Lúcio Quintal, ARDITI (Madeira)

Members and field of expertise: 65 registrations.

TWG 6 Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and biosystems engineering

Definition: The nine ORs are significant areas linked to resources (agriculture, forestry...) offering opportunities for developing for example the **circular economy** and making them important players in governance. Their rich biodiversity – a buffer against storm and flood surges, is also the basis for key economic sectors. Some scientific domains of expertise and policy objectives are:

- Water treatment and waste water management.
- Agroecology and Valorization of bioresources (phytopharmacy and phytocosmetics).
- Quality of agrofood, food supplements and food security.
- Renewal of the agri-food industries by developing specific expertise and products.
- Bioproducts and biosystems engineering.
- Bioeconomy.
- Micro-organisms, pathology and molecular genetics: development of genome innovations for selecting varieties adapted to tropical production.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment) & (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3.

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Jean-Christophe Bambou, INRAE (Guadelupe) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: -
- Facilitator: Emyly Guyon and Jean-François Dorville, Synergile (Guadeloupe)

Members and field of expertise: 59 registrations.

TWG 7 Biodiversity conservation & restoration

Definition: ORs are among the most ecologically vulnerable territories of the Union. Indeed, their small size, isolation and high level of endemic biodiversity, make them particularly exposed to anthropogenic and climate-change induced dynamics threatening natural ecosystems on a global scale and the communities which rely on them. It is also a way to turn a threat into an opportunity by positioning outermost regions as living labs of biodiversity conservation and restoration. Some scientific domains of expertise and policy objectives are:

- Biodiversity, Ecology & Conservation of species and ecosystems.
- Biogeography and evolutionary processes.
- Ecology, Evolution and Interactions in Caribbean, Macaronesian and Indian Ocean Area, and Amazonian systems.
- Conservation of natural heritage & Understanding of heritage and landscape.
- Invasive alien species and other environmental risks.
- Biosphere conservation, social-environmental conflicts, greening of public action.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment) & (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3.

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Paulo Borges, University of Azores (Azores) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: Mário Boeiro, University of Azores (Azores)
- Facilitators: Carolina Parelho and Lina Silveira, FRCT and Nuno Vasconcelos, UAc (Azores)

Members and field of expertise: 63 registrations.

TWG 8 Marine sciences & technologies

Definition: The nine ORs significant exclusive economic zones linked to marine resources (aquaculture, biodiversity, fisheries...) and are in the front line of climate change, which threatens the use of seas, ocean and coasts and calls for innovative and technological solutions, offering opportunities for developing the blue economy and making them important players in international ocean governance. Some scientific domains of expertise and policy objectives are:

- Aquaculture and fisheries.
- Biodiversity, Ecology and Conservation, Coral reef health.
- Desalination systems for water scarcity affected regions with high insolation.
- Marine spatial planning and management of marine resources and ecosystems.
- Marine renewable energies, hydrogen, off-shore wind energy, wave energy, floating solar panels, ocean thermal energy.
- Marine multiuse platforms.
- Maritime-tourist sector.
- Science and technologies of the sea.
- Oceanography.

Alignment with Horizon Europe: Horizon Europe Pillar 1, Pillar 2 (Cluster: Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment) & (Cluster: civil security for society) and Pillar 3

Management team:

- Sub-coordinator: Ricardo Haroun, University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Canary Islands) / [CV](#)
- Deputy: Francisco Otero Ferrer, University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Canary Islands)
- Facilitators: Almudena Suárez and Noelia Díaz, ULPGC (Canary Islands)

Members and field of expertise: 76 registrations.

4 Thematic Action Plan methodology

This methodology is a reference for the work of thematic working groups, in order to define their thematic action plans. The thematic action plans will be produced by each TWG sub coordinator's team after the first transnational meeting, in cooperation with the TWG members. This methodology will be covered during the initial training, with the following topics:

4.1 Designing and implementing the strategy

Re-definition of research areas an organizational structure

Each TWG must analyse the research fields and subjects included in the definition of the working group, prioritizing those with a higher potential impact, based on the capacities and strengths of the TWG members and the ORs involved. The TWG can also add new research fields or modify the existing ones. If necessary, sub-groups could be implemented for different research fields or areas of specialization.

Setting the objectives

Once each TWG has a clear definition of its mission and vision, and how they are going to afford it, they must set their specific objectives taking into account the general objectives: ***establishment of networks between the OR and external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects as well as implementation of the activities envisaged in a specific domain***, the general management objectives and also the necessary dissemination activities.

Specific objectives definition means stating clearly what each TWG wants to achieve, what needs to be accomplished to implement the strategy. Specific objectives are concrete attainments that can be achieved by following a certain number of steps. They must be concrete, must be written, and they should be S.M.A.R.T.

- ***Specific:*** The objective should be as concrete as possible.
- ***Measurable:*** The objective must be quantifiable.
- ***Achievable:*** The objective must be ambitious, a challenge for the TWG, but attainable.
- ***Realistic:*** Objectives must be set within the TWG means, taking into account the available resources.
- ***Timely:*** Deadlines must be defined.

There are different tools to support TWGs in setting their strategies and objectives, some of them will be presented in the initial training.

Measuring the effectiveness of the TWGs requires choosing the right metrics. The selected indicators should enable to obtain information on the overall performance of each TWG.

4.2 Action Plan Development

The action plan should include the specific objectives and a summary of the proposed actions and total combined number of expected outputs and outcomes of all partners involved in the TWG (See Annex Action Plan Template).

In this action plan, each TWG should include, among other activities:

- Transregional meetings between sub-coordinators.
- TWG Meetings.
- Trainings.
- Local, national, international events.
- Meetings/ events with external stakeholders.
- Networking activities.
- Reports, documents, deliverables to be prepared by the TWG.
- Supporting actions to promote the participation of ORs organization in European Programmes.
- Dissemination activities (web page, newsletter, press releases, social media, ...)

The activities related with other work packages (WP4 capacity building, WP5 networking activities, WP8 communication and dissemination) will be planned in coordination with the WP leaders.

The local/ regional activities will be planned in close cooperation with the Regional Coordinator of R&I community.

4.3 Results and deliverables

Each TWG must clearly identify the expected results and deliverables and their deadlines, including:

- Thematic Action Plan (*first version in October 2020, to be updated continuously*)
- TWG members list.
- Achievements: list measurable results of the actions.
- Calendar with milestones.
- TWG Meetings Minutes.

It is also recommended that TWGs develop:

- Funding Opportunities and Supporting Programmes Catalogue: a document with all the identified European funding opportunities for the specific research areas (R&D Projects, networks, training, exchanges, innovation,...), as well as other supporting programmes (Enterprise Europe Network, European Innovation Partnerships, S3 Platform, Digital Innovation Hubs, ...).
- Profiles Database: a document with the R&D&I organization's profiles (organisation name, type, description, address, areas of activity, contact data) and also what their offers/ requests (product, service, partnership, project cooperation, investment opportunity). This information can be used in different networks, events, online tools to search for the suitable partners for these organizations.

5 Annexes

Annex I TWGs List of members / registrations

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
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Annex II TWGs Action plan template

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- Prospective and strategic exercises to identify critical research fields and subjects in the ORs;
- Establishment of **networks** between the ORs and external actors that will cooperate to build **critical masses** and **projects** on the considered thematics;
- Implementation of the activities envisaged in a specific domain.
- Prospective approach to focus on ensuring their **sustainability** both during the project life and even after its end.

TWG: Number and title of the TWG

Version	Date							
N°	Actions	Details/ Venue	Start/end	Resources	Contact Person (Member of the TWG in charge of this activity)	Other co-organizers (Members of the TWG involved in this activity)	Expected results	Level of advancement
1	Specific Objective 1							
1.1	Activity 1.1							
1.1.1	Task 1.1.1							
1.1.2	Task 1.1.2							
1.2	Activity 1.2							
1.2.1	Task 1.2.1							
1.2.2	Task 1.2.2							
1.3	Activity 1.3							
2	Specific Objective 2							
2.1	Activity 2.1							
2.1.1	Task 2.1.1							
2.1.2	Task 2.1.2							
2.2	Activity 2.2							
2.2.1	Task 2.2.1							
2.2.2	Task 2.2.2							

			2020						2021											
			July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
TWG Objectives	Actions	Deliverables																		
Obj 1	Action 1																			
	Action 2																			
	Action 3																			
Obj 2	Action 1																			
	Action 2																			
	Action 3																			
	Action 4																			
Obj 3	Action 1																			
	Action 2																			

Include milestones